

Telepresence Robotics and AI-Based Services for Older Adults @Home Assistance

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Abstract—This abstract summarizes aspects of the on-going effort to synthesize a telepresence application for home assistance within the SI-Robotics project. Key aspect of SI-Robotics is the integration of state-of-the-art Robotics, AI and sensors to produce added-value services for ecological assistance for older people staying at home.

Index Terms—telepresence robots, remote home assistance, elderly people, Robotics&AI

I. INTRODUCTION

The SocIal ROBOTics for active and healthy ageing project (SI-ROBOTICS) aims at designing and developing new assistive solutions to provide continuous support to elderly people in different scenarios (e.g., houses, hospitals, health residences, rehabilitative facilities). A specific line of investigation in the project focuses on domestic scenarios where telepresence robots are introduced with the dual purposes of: (a) being a companion for the *primary user* (i.e., the elderly); (b) being an intelligent intermediary for the *secondary users* (i.e., the remote users) to monitor and to interact with the person at home. While the telepresence robots have to operate in the out-of-the lab environments resulting still a challenge for roboticists, the secondary users are different typologies such as family members, doctors, caregivers, friends, that need a robust cloud infrastructure to communicate through the robot [1]. In this scenario, we are facing the research question about how to allow a continuous interaction and assistance in the long-term perspective to promote the stay of the elderly people in the natural environment where they always live [2]. To achieve this ambitious goal, we identify two main requirements which are driving the design and the development of our telepresence robots: (a) the personalization of the interaction according to both the typology of users and the evolution of over time of their needs, (b) the execution of some robot's behaviors in autonomy. These behaviors are designed to help the remote teleoperation by assigning the low-level tasks to the robot including the obstacle avoidance, target reaching and the adjustment of the orientation towards the person with which interact without requiring the intervention of the external operator. These aspects spotlight the necessity of including services operating at two levels of abstraction:

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the first category based on the reasoning, the representation of the information and the profiling, the second associated with the reactive execution and adaptation of the scheduled tasks to the dynamic evolution of the world. In other words, we are pursuing the strategy to exploit planning and scheduling functionalities to personalise services and distribute them considering the entire temporal horizon, while a set of *on-board* services is in charge of operating locally and adjust the tasks in accordance with the local data from robot's perception considering the information not known *a priori* [3].

This partition of the services is in line with the architecture proposed by other works in the literature [4], [5]. Recently De Benedictis et al. [6] have demonstrated its efficacy in the case of adaptive dialogue between the robot and the elderly people. With respect to previous works, herein, we extend the same approach to enhance the capabilities of a commercial telepresence robot via heterogeneous services. Thus, on the one side, the degree of complexity is exploding with the increasing of the services, on the other it arises the limitation of strict resources and capability available on a commercial robot. Finally, we are designing specific services taking into account the emphatic and the privacy constraints to provide human-centered and ecological assistance over the time.

II. ROBOTIC PLATFORM & DEVELOPING ENVIRONMENT

Our telepresence platform is the Ohmni robot. It is a differential mobile robot endowed with two RGB cameras and a 2D lidar respectively for telepresence and navigation purposes (see Fig. 1). The platform supports the de-facto standard *Robot Operating System* (ROS) via a *Docker virtualization* layer on which the *on-board* services run. To facilitate the development, we also design a custom simulator based on Gazebo emulating the robot and its sensors.

III. TELEPRESENCE AND AI-BASED SERVICES

Since our aim consists in creating a telepresence robot for the long-term assistance of elderly people, as anticipated, we are promoting the integration of robotics and AI-based services inside the same architecture to endow the robot with the abilities of sophisticated reasoning and the adaptive execution of the expected reactive services. In particular, we are designing four main kinds of functionalities oriented to the: (a) personalized interaction with both typologies of users; (b) the contextualized navigation and the implementation of robot's behaviors in autonomy; (c) an augmented robot's perception

Fig. 1. The telepresence and the AI-based services on the proposed platform.

to achieve emphatic interaction; and (d) the planning and the scheduling of the daily activities where the robot is a support for the users. Moreover, in accordance with the needs emerged from the recent studies on telepresence including [7], [8], we assign the robot an active role on the continuous monitoring of the elderly people to avoid cognitive and physical decline over the time. With this purpose, the robot is exploited as medium to engage primary users in cognitive and physical exercises during the day as well as an intermediary to provide feedback about their physiological status to them and to their caregivers.

IV. THE DEVELOPMENT CHALLENGES

Beyond the functionalities, the first challenge consists of introducing a knowledge and causal reasoning that flexibly cooperates with the *on board* services. Indeed, it is therefore important, once a solution is generated, to adapt it to the possible unpredictable changes that may emerge during its implementation in the real world. In the case of planning, in particular, these types of adaptations can involve delays in the start or end of planned activities, but also the failure of some tasks or the addition of new unplanned tasks, maintaining the domain constraints valid. By analysing the provided *on-board* services, they are classified into two categories as shown in Fig. 1: a) the ones directly acquiring and processing the raw information coming from the robot's sensors (e.g., detection of obstacle, detection of people, detection of the emotions), b) the other relying on the previous ones but elaborating the data to implement actions such as the contextualized navigation, the sessions of the cognitive and physical exercises. In both cases, a significant challenge consists of developing advanced robotics and vision algorithms able to run with a very limited computing power and resources. To overcome this issue, for instance, we have designed an emotion detection algorithms exploiting a thin deep architecture with only 3.9M number of parameters with respect to the 50-100M necessary in the standard approaches, reaching the 87.71% of average accuracy. The same is true for the skeleton detection and tracking service for which we chose to wrapper the *MediaPipe Pose* library inside ROS, since it is able to achieve good real-time performance also in mobile phone without requiring GPU with respect to the traditional algorithms in robotics such as *OpenPose* and *SPENCER People Tracking*. Secondly, we are facing the problem of guaranteeing the people privacy, in par-

ticular by formulating *policies* for the activation/deactivation of the microphone and the camera. Both are enabled only with the person's consensus when: a) the person touches the robot, b) the person answers "yes" when required by the robot (e.g., activate the microphone when a person is detected). Thirdly, to facilitate the driving of the robot from remote users, we are including *shared autonomy* navigation that allows the robot semi-autonomously move in the environment from only few directional person's commands. The robot performs some behaviors chosen a priori in autonomy, including the people search in the domestic environment triggering the interaction. Finally, once known the scheduled activity from the planner, one of the substantial challenge consists of orchestrating the different services. This aspect is locally managed by a module, that we call *local task manager*, that is in charge of outlining the specific pipeline necessary to execute the scheduled activity from the high-level description and thus, of enabling/deactivating the specific low-level services. For instance, when the *interaction with person* is chosen by the planner, the robot should be able to automatically verify the presence of person, then to place at the suitable distance and activate the *text-to-speech* and *speech-to-text* functionality for the interactive dialogue.

V. CONCLUSION

We synthesized the salient aspects and the challenges guiding the development of a new generation of telepresence robots for the long-term interaction. In the ongoing experimentation, we are testing the feasibility and the integration of the proposed services with a commercial telepresence robot with standard capabilities and we are validating the ecological interaction with final potential users.

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